

Recommended Practice: Ontology creation, publication, and maintenance for wind energy domain experts

Yuriy Marykovskiy¹, Jean-Paul Calbimonte², Sarah Barber^{1,*}

¹ Institute for Energy Technology (IET), Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences (OST), Rapperswil-Jona, Switzerland

² Institute of Informatics, University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland (HES-SO), Sierre, Switzerland

* Co-Operating Agent for IEA Wind Task 43

Executive Summary

The digitalisation of the wind energy sector is essential for improving interoperability and data sharing among stakeholders, supporting advancements in technologies like Intelligent Digital Twins. However, the lack of common, community-adopted information models hinders seamless information exchange and knowledge management. These topics fall under the area of knowledge engineering, and specifically, knowledge representation and ontology engineering. This Recommended Practice first introduces ontologies of various degrees of expressivity as means of knowledge representation for wind energy domain experts and outlines several use cases. It details a collaborative, community-driven approach for ontology development, drawing on the existing Methontology and Ontology Development 101 methodologies and leveraging open-source practices for sustainable development and community engagement. Existing software tools are then presented and put into perspective to streamline the modelling and publishing process, minimising overhead in terms of manual effort and technical complexity, while ensuring adherence to FAIR principles. The Recommended Practice is intended as a step-by-step guidance for the formalisation and publication of information models in the form of ontologies, contributing to industry-wide improvements in data management, data engineering, artificial intelligence systems development, and decision-making.

Introduction

Comprehensive digitalisation of the wind energy sector is one of the current challenges faced by both industry and academia. According to [ETIPWind](#), digitalisation is one of the five Megatrends in wind energy technology today. This effort plays a fundamental role in enabling frictionless information exchange within organisations and across various collaborators and interest groups. The automation in information exchange and interoperability are essential in the creation of artificial intelligence systems, such as Intelligent Digital Twins, and hence form a cornerstone of the digitalisation process, ultimately resulting in a value creation for the actors in the sector. To achieve interoperability, it is required to introduce common information models that are adopted by domain stakeholders and are continually adapted on the basis of the continuously evolving environment (Marykovskiy et al., 2024). An information model is a structured representation of concepts and their relationships, constraints, rules, which describes data semantics (i.e. meaning) within a specific domain. The term is often used interchangeably with conceptual model, depending on the context. Depending on the formalisation and complexity, or specific application context, information models may also be known by other related terms such as *controlled vocabulary*, *taxonomy*, *schema*, *ontology* or *semantic artefact*. In the context of knowledge engineering and knowledge representation, which deals with the formalisation, structuring, and management of knowledge, it is common to use the term ontology.

Ontology is defined as “*explicit specification of a conceptualisation*” by Gruber (1993). “Conceptualisation”, in Gruber’s definition, refers to an abstract view or model of the world, i.e. the types of objects, concepts, and other entities that are assumed to exist in a domain of interest and their associated properties, relationships and relationship constraints. “Explicit” means that these concepts, relationships, rules, and the constraints are explicitly defined by expressing them in formal language that adheres to well-defined syntax and semantics.

In the context of digitalising the wind energy sector, employing ontologies allows for a rich and precise formalisation of the domain’s knowledge, which can vary from something as limited in scope as defining blade anomaly terms, or inference rules for Failure Modes Effects and criticality analysis to comprehensively covering an entire wind energy domain. Given the complex, dynamic and evolving nature of the sector, ontologies must be designed to be modular, extensible, and interoperable with other domain ontologies. Following ontology engineering best practices, such as modular design, use of ontology design methodologies, and alignment with upper-level ontologies, ensures that domain knowledge and data remain findable, interoperable and reusable.

For a primer on knowledge engineering in wind energy refer to “*Knowledge engineering for wind energy*” (Marykovskiy et al., 2024). This document provides a comprehensive overview of key concepts, challenges, and practical applications of knowledge engineering techniques in the wind sector. It discusses topics such as knowledge representation, semantic data integration, ontology development, and their roles in enhancing digitalisation efforts. Readers are encouraged to familiarise themselves with this primer to better appreciate the foundational concepts that underpin this Recommended Practice and to understand the broader context of knowledge-driven digital transformation in wind energy. Alternatively, readers may refer to the

Common Information Model (CIM) Primer (EPRI, 2022), which provides a broader introduction to knowledge representation concepts and information modeling languages, before focusing on applications within the electrical energy sector, specifically, on power system modeling, including transmission, distribution, and market operations.

The present Recommended Practice builds on these foundations by providing concrete guidance for the development, formalisation, and publication of information models in the form of ontologies, specifically tailored to support community-driven efforts within the wind energy sector.

Ontology coverage and scope

Before diving into ontology development, it is important to clearly define the intended coverage and scope of the semantic models.

Recommended Practice: Ensure ontology alignment with existing semantic artefacts

It is common to differentiate between *top-level*, *domain-level*, and *application/task-level* ontologies based on their degree of abstraction, scope, and specificity, ranging from highly generalised concepts applicable across multiple domains, through specialised terminologies and relationships specific to particular domains, down to detailed, use-case driven, conceptualisations developed for particular applications or tasks (Guarino, 1998).

Top-level ontologies serve as foundational reference models that define general concepts - such as object, quality, or process - applicable universally across various domains. As ontologies are developed for specific domains or applications, adoption of common top level ontologies becomes essential to ensure alignment and interoperability. Partridge et al. (2020) performed a comprehensive overview of top level ontologies which have achieved significant adoption across various areas to inform the selection of suitable foundational models to guide ontology development in the domain of interest. Among existing top level ontologies, this recommendation would like to point out *Basic Formal Ontology (BFO)*, *Common Core Ontologies (CCO)*, and more specialised top level conceptualisations like *Dublin Core (DC)* and *Schema.org*. Before taking on the task of the ontology development it is opportune to familiarise with these ontologies to ensure alignment and reuse.

Domain-level ontologies capture knowledge specific to a domain of interest. Currently, within the wind energy context, there is no established domain ontology. The Wind Energy Ontology (WEO) is a domain ontology currently under development under the auspices of the [WeDoWind Information Modelling](#) community and [IEA Wind Task 43](#), to serve as a middle layer between top-level ontologies and specialised, application and task-level conceptualisations. WEO aims to provide a high-level representation of wind energy concepts, aligned with existing mid-level models such as *Open Energy Ontology* (Emele et al., 2024), *Ontologies Foundry Core (IOF-Core)* (Drobnjakovic et al., 2022), that are already aligned with BFO, and more specialised, application-specific models such as *Reference Designation Standards for Wind Power Systems*

([RDS for WPS](#)) or the classification of blade damage recommended by Electric Power Research Institute (EPRI).

Application/task-level ontologies are designed to support specific processes, tasks, or application scenarios within a domain. They define specialised terminologies, explicit relationships, and constraints for the purpose of knowledge representation at the granular level required for specific use cases. An example of such ontology is the Failure Mode, Effects, and Criticality Analysis for Wind Turbines (FMECA4WT) developed by Zhou et al. (2015).

This Recommended Practice is focused on the development of application and task ontologies, which should ultimately align with the broader structure and semantic commitments of WEO.

Ontology expressiveness and development complexity

Recommended Practice: Balance expressiveness with simplicity

Another aspect to consider before initiating ontology development is the tradeoff between the expressiveness of the ontology and the complexity involved in its development and use. Expressiveness impacts the kinds of relationships, rules, and constraints that can be formally represented, and thus directly affects the capabilities of automated reasoning, data integration, and semantic querying. As an example, Table 1 contains a non-exhaustive list of use cases along with related expressiveness.

Controlled vocabularies, thesauri, and taxonomies

Controlled vocabularies, thesauri, and taxonomies are simpler forms of ontologies.

- A controlled vocabulary is a curated list of terms used consistently for data annotation.
- A thesaurus extends a controlled vocabulary with hierarchical and associative relationships (e.g., broader/narrower terms).
- A taxonomy is a hierarchical classification of concepts, where terms are arranged according to their parent-child relationships.

While these are conceptually simpler than fully-fledged ontologies, they can be seen as lightweight semantic models, or less expressive ontologies, which provide structure and consistency without the complexity of logical formalism.

To formalise these basic structures, the *Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS)* data model is recommended as a starting point. SKOS provides a standardised way to represent controlled vocabularies, thesauri, and taxonomies using RDF (Resource Description Framework), allowing easier sharing and reuse. SKOS is particularly well-suited for domain

experts unfamiliar with formal ontology languages such as OWL (Web Ontology Language), offering a gentle entry point into semantic modelling.

Ontologies

For more complex knowledge representation needs, full ontologies built with RDF and OWL are recommended. RDF provides a flexible way for representing information in a graph-like structure, while OWL extends RDF to allow formal logic-based representation of classes, properties, constraints, and complex relationships, supporting reasoning and consistency checking.

OWL ontologies enable advanced capabilities such as automated classification of instances, inference of implicit knowledge, and complex query answering. However, this power comes with increased modelling and computational complexity, making it necessary to balance expressiveness with usability and performance based on project needs.

Knowledge graphs

Knowledge graphs (KGs) are a flexible and increasingly popular approach to representing interconnected data in a graph structure, where entities are nodes and relationships are edges. Hogan et al., 2021 provide an introduction to the KGs and discuss how these graph-based data models not only can be used to capture knowledge, but also to perform knowledge inference. Unlike traditional databases, KGs offer semantic richness and flexibility, allowing the same dataset to be queried, extended, and reasoned about in highly dynamic and scalable ways. KGs can be constructed based on formal ontologies, using standards like RDF and OWL, but they can also be more loosely structured, relying only on lightweight semantics or no formal semantics at all.

An essential technology for querying RDF-based knowledge graphs is SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language). SPARQL enables expressive queries over graph-structured data, such as finding entities with certain properties, traversing relationships, and inferring new knowledge based on existing triples.

While ontology-backed KGs provide the advantage of formal reasoning (e.g., consistency checking, classification), many real-world KGs, such as those built with Neo4j or other property graph databases, focus more on practical data integration and retrieval without necessarily using formal ontology languages. These lighter-weight KGs often prioritise ease of use and performance over strict logical consistency.

In practice, there are two general strategies for the development of knowledge graphs with ontological backbone:

- *Top-down approach:* Ontologies are first carefully developed to define the structure and semantics of the domain. Data is then populated into a knowledge graph based on these predefined ontological structures. This method ensures consistency and semantic rigor

but requires significant upfront effort.

- *Bottom-up approach*: A large amount of factual data (triples) is first collected and organised into a knowledge graph, often with minimal initial semantics. Ontologies are then gradually extracted or built over time by identifying recurring patterns, types, and relationships. This approach is more agile and scalable for exploratory domains but may result in less consistency without careful curation.

Choosing between these approaches, or combining them, depends heavily on the maturity of the domain knowledge, the availability of data, and the goals of the knowledge engineering project.

Table 1. Non-exhaustive list of use cases along with related expressiveness.

Use Case	Recommended Expressiveness / Technologies	Notes	Example Queries / Questions
Basic terminology management (e.g., blade anomaly types)	Controlled Vocabulary / SKOS	Simple term lists; minimal structure; no reasoning needed.	"What are all defined blade anomaly types?" "Give me the definition of 'leading edge erosion'."
Hierarchical classification of turbine components	Taxonomy / SKOS	Parent-child relationships (broader/narrower concepts).	"List all subcomponents of a turbine nacelle." "What is the parent category of 'gearbox'?"
Tagging and feature search of activities	Thesaurus / SKOS	Includes associative (related) relationships.	"What maintenance tasks are related to lubrication?" "Find activities related to the decommissioning life-cycle stage ."
Data cataloguing and metadata description	Controlled Vocabulary / SKOS + Dublin Core	Metadata enrichment; focus on descriptions.	"Which datasets describe blade inspection activity?" "In what external conditions was the turbine SCADA data collected?"
Knowledge integration from multiple maintenance systems	Lightweight Ontology (RDFS / OWL Lite)	Class and property alignment across systems.	"Link failure reports from different CMS vendors." "Map 'temperature alert' events across systems."
Validation of incoming sensor data structures	SHACL Shapes + Lightweight Ontology (RDFS) + Linked Data	Data validation of incoming graphs.	"Does the turbine status data conform to the expected schema?" "Are all mandatory fields populated?"
Knowledge grounding (vector-based semantic retrieval with LLMs)	Lightweight Ontology + Embedding Index + RAG architecture	Link formal terms to retrieved documents via embeddings.	"Retrieve documents mentioning similar anomalies to 'tip shear'." "Find texts describing gearbox overheating."

Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) for turbine maintenance FAQs	Lightweight Ontology + Knowledge Graph + Embeddings	Ontology structures content, embeddings enable fast retrieval. Results in non-deterministic informal answers.	"What is the recommended action for a generator vibration alarm?" "Summarise common gearbox issues."
Predictive maintenance and failure inference	Highly Expressive Ontology (OWL DL)	Requires axioms and inference.	"Which components have a high failure risk after a blade pitch system error?" "Predict potential failure chains from sensor alerts."
Advanced formal reasoning using logical rules	Highly Expressive Ontology (OWL DL + SWRL Rules)	Adds custom logic beyond OWL expressiveness; enables automated inference of complex situations based on domain-specific rules.	"Infer that a turbine needs urgent maintenance if vibration > threshold AND oil temperature > threshold." "What are the end effects of a transformer shaft roller bearing failure?"
Smart semantic search across operational datasets	Lightweight Ontology + Knowledge Graph (RDF + SKOS)	Semantic search across datasets with aligned concepts.	"Find turbine downtime events associated with high wind speeds." "Search for all critical component replacements in Q2."
Complex SPARQL querying for anomaly pattern detection	OWL DL Ontology + SPARQL	Logical inferences + structured queries.	"List turbines with repeated gearbox sensor anomalies in past 30 days." "Detect patterns linking wind shear and blade damage reports."
User-friendly querying using query rewriting	Lightweight or Expressive Ontology (OWL Lite/OWL DL) + Query Rewriting Engine	Simplifies complex SPARQL queries for end-users; system translates high-level queries to formal SPARQL queries automatically.	"Which turbines had a blade issue last month?" → automatically rewritten to a SPARQL query that expands 'blade anomaly' into detailed classes (e.g., cracks, debond, etc). "Find maintenance events linked to critical components."
Digital Twin modeling for performance optimisation	Expressive Ontology + Knowledge Graph (OWL DL + RDF) + Workflow modelling	High expressiveness needed for real-time events and workflow modelling.	"Predict turbine output under current blade wear conditions." "Recommend actions to maximise turbine uptime this month."
Exploratory search and dynamic dashboard visualisations	Knowledge Graph (RDF + SPARQL) (Minimal Ontology)	Flexible visual exploration.	"Show turbines ordered by current performance metrics." "Visualise failure rates by component type."
Extraction of design rules from historical maintenance data	Bottom-Up KG -> Ontology (Data-first, then structure)	Learn from facts; abstract patterns later.	"Identify recurring failure modes from 5-year maintenance history." "Suggest turbine designs with fewer drivetrain failures."
Linking turbine operational models with environmental data	Lightweight Ontology + Linked Data principles	RDF links across datasets, minimal axioms needed.	"Link SCADA operational data with local weather events." "Correlate turbine curtailment events with bird migration data."

Ontology development, publishing, and adoption life-cycle

We propose an approach for community-driven wind energy domain information model creation, based on Gomez-Perez et al., 1997, with a specific focus on community engagement. The workflow for this approach is visualised in Figure 2 and detailed in the sections below

1. Initiation

Working group creation

Recommended Practice: Form working groups combining domain experts and knowledge engineers

The starting point of the approach is the creation of working groups based on the preliminary consultation with the wider community. These working groups should include people with some knowledge engineering or data management experience to assist in ontology development, along with domain and specific topic experts.

Recommended Practice: Use collaborative platforms

Working groups can be organised using collaborative platforms such as:

- Mailing lists and RSS feeds
- Web pages and wikis
- Shared workspaces (Google Workspace, Microsoft Teams)
- Collaborative versioning systems (GitHub, GitLab)
- Digital collaboration platforms (Mighty Networks, Discord, Circle)

The *WeDoWind Information Modelling Community* offers a digital communication platform to initiate and host such working groups, providing access to shared resources and a knowledge base. Moreover, within the [WeDoWind](#) platform there is a possibility to interact with other related communities such as a collaborative problem-solving community and a data users' community.

Ontology selection

Recommended Practice: Define a clear application use case before starting ontology work

Once a core working group is formed, the next step is to identify a specific task or application for which the ontology is required. This can be achieved through domain review, open community discussion, and prioritisation via voting. Selection criteria should consider the impact, feasibility, and availability of experts.

Figure 1. Ontology development, publishing, and adoption life-cycle

2. Development

Recommended Practice: Follow established methods for ontology development

The core of the workflow is focused on the iterative development of an ontology. We refer to the Ontology Development 101 method (Noy and McGuinness, 2001) and Unified Process for Ontology Building: UPON (De Nicola et al. (2005)) for a detailed discussion of ontology development methods. UPON is particularly well suited for the development of application and task ontologies, which are the interest of this Recommended Practice.

Development tools and automation

Recommended Practice: Manage artefacts with version control

Inspired by open-source community practices, it is recommended to use Git for version control. Each semantic artefact can have a dedicated GitHub / GitLab repository, enabling:

- Version control
- Branching and parallel development
- Continuous integration of changes
- Community feedback through pull requests and issues

Recommended Practice: Automate validation and publishing

For simple artefacts (e.g., SKOS taxonomies), a shared spreadsheet template can be used to gather concepts and relationships collaboratively. Tools such as *xls2rdf* can automatically convert these spreadsheets into RDF models, with GitHub Actions enabling automated validation and publishing. Examples of such GitHub repositories can be found on [WeDoWind GitHub page](#).

Other available tools include:

- SKOS Play! for SKOS visualisation
- VocBench for SKOS development, visualisation and web hosting

In cases when a full ontology is required (such as an application ontology), an ontology creation and editing tool such as Protégé can be utilised. A web version of the Protégé tool - WebProtégé - provides a collaborative ontology development environment that allows users to create, edit, and share ontologies online, without the need for locally installed software.

Engagement of domain specialists

Recommended Practice: Engage the wider community with open calls and interactive reviews

Beyond the core development team, broader engagement can be achieved through:

- Periodic review meetings
- Public calls for feedback (GitHub Discussions, WeDoWind Feeds, Linked posts)
- Webinars and topic workshops
- Interactive review (e.g., WebProtégé, Git pulls, etc.)

Prototype development and evaluation

Recommended Practice: Test early prototypes in real-world applications

Early prototypes of the ontology should be released for evaluation in real-world applications, assessing usability, coverage, and interoperability. An iterative approach is recommended. This can be done in collaborations with commercial organisations providing implementation examples or as part of research project consortia or international collaborations such as IEA Wind TCP.

3. Publishing and maintenance

Recommended Practice: Make ontologies FAIR

It is important for the developed ontologies to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) (Wilkinson et al., 2016) themselves. Following the FAIR principles, once released on GitHub, the repository can be set up for automatic archiving on Zenodo, ensuring persistence and providing a persistent Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for each model version. Moreover, ontologies should be made available for searching, reference, and viewing. This is typically achieved through publishing them on ontology hosting catalogues, assigning persistent URL namespaces, and creating documentation web pages.

Ontology hosting catalogues

Recommended Practice: Publish ontologies on TechnoPortal or IndustryPortal

OntoPortal Appliance is an open source web-based software for creating ontology catalogs. It is already used as a basis by BioPortal serving the biomedical community, AgroPortal for hosting the agri-food domain ontologies, and MatPortal hosting material sciences ontologies. Wind energy domain ontologies can be published on the recently created [TechnoPortal](#), which serves as a go to catalogue for the engineering and technology domain ontologies. Alternatively, [IndustryPortal](#) hosts industry-specific ontologies.

Internationalized Resource Identifiers (IRIs) and Persistent URLs

Recommended Practice: Assign versioned IRIs to all stable ontology releases

Each concept, property, or instance within an ontology is identified by an *Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI)*. An IRI is a globally unique identifier, very similar to a URL but allowing a wider range of characters (including non-ASCII characters), making it suitable for international use. In older standards, the term Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) was used, but IRIs extend URIs to support international characters.

In ontologies, IRIs are critical because they:

- Serve as stable identifiers for knowledge elements (e.g., a wind turbine model, wind turbine part, a measurement property)
- Enable linking and integration of datasets and ontologies across the web
- Support machine-readable and human-readable representations

However, maintaining the stability of IRIs over time can be challenging, especially as hosting infrastructures, repositories, or organisations evolve. If an ontology is moved or the organisation managing it changes its servers, hard-coded IRIs could break, which results in broken references.

To prevent this, Persistent URLs (PURLs) are used. A PURL acts as a *stable redirect* that points to the current actual location of an ontology or its resources. This ensures that even if the ontology moves, its IRI remains stable and valid.

Setting up PURLs for ontology IRIs ensures:

- Long-term stability of references
- Compliance with FAIR principles (especially "Findable" and "Accessible")
- Trustworthiness and adoption in broader communities and linked data ecosystems

Services such as purl.org and w3id.org allow ontology creators to register PURLs that redirect transparently to the latest hosting location of their ontology files or documentation. The readers are advised to refer to the specific service's documentation on the steps required to register PURLs.

PURLs are designed to provide stable, long-term web addresses for ontology resources. In line with the FAIR principles, registering a PURL allows an ontology's IRI to remain accessible even if its physical location or hosting infrastructure changes. However, to ensure that PURLs fulfill their intended role as persistent identifiers, they should only be registered once the ontology has reached a sufficient level of maturity.

Recommended Practice: Delay PURL registration until ontology stabilisation

As summarised in Table 2, PURLs should not be registered for ontologies that are in early stages of development or undergoing frequent structural revisions. Registering a PURL too early may lead to broken links or references to obsolete content, undermining both interoperability and user trust. The following practices are recommended before registering a PURL:

- *Version Stability.* The ontology should have reached a stable release, typically marked by a versioned IRI (e.g., <https://example.org/ontology/v1.0>). This ensures that any external reference to the ontology via its PURL corresponds to a well-defined and documented state of the model.
- *Separation of Development and Release Artefacts.* Developers should maintain a clear separation between development and production versions of the ontology. Experimental or unstable drafts should use temporary or non-persistent IRIs, while mature releases should be associated with permanent IRIs and corresponding PURLs.
- *Established Documentation and Accessibility.* Before PURL registration, the ontology should be published in a human-readable and accessible format, such as documentation generated using the Live OWL Documentation Environment (LODE). The PURL should resolve directly to this documentation, thereby supporting both human and machine accessibility in alignment with FAIR principles.
- *Metadata and Licensing.* The ontology should be accompanied by appropriate metadata, including title, description, authorship, versioning information, and licensing terms. This ensures clarity for reuse and supports cataloguing in ontology registries and portals.
- *Automated Release and Maintenance Workflows.* It is recommended to integrate the ontology publishing process into automated workflows (e.g., via GitHub Actions), enabling reproducible releases, validation, and timely updates to the linked PURL destination.

Table 2. Recommendation for PURL registration dependent on ontology development stage.

Ontology Development Stage	PURL Registration	Justification
Initial prototyping	Not recommended	High likelihood of structural and semantic change
Internal review / beta release	Provisionally	Suitable for testing; use a preview PURL with limited scope
Public stable release	Strongly recommended	Ontology has stable structure, versioning, and documentation

Live OWL Documentation Environment (LODE)

Recommended Practice: Provide machine- and human-readable documentation

The Live OWL Documentation Environment (LODE) offers an interactive means to generate human-readable documentation directly from OWL or RDF ontologies. LODE automates the production of comprehensive, clean, and navigable documentation that outlines classes, properties, axioms, and other ontology constructs. Integrating LODE into the publishing workflow benefits both ontology developers and users by:

- Providing immediate, up-to-date documentation that reflects the current state of the ontology
- Supporting the dissemination and persistence of domain knowledge through a well-structured, accessible documentation platform

In practice, incorporating LODE involves configuring it to pull the latest version of the ontology from the GitHub repository. This automated approach ensures that the documentation remains current with every update.

Recommended Practice: IRI Resolution to documentation pages

It is considered good practice for an ontology's IRI to resolve to human-readable documentation, such as one generated by LODE.

This set-up ensures that:

- When users dereference an ontology IRI via a web browser, they are presented with clear, understandable documentation, rather than raw RDF/OWL serialisation
- It enhances the accessibility and usability of the ontology
- It simplifies learning and reuse by new users and facilitates broader community adoption

In practice, this can be achieved through HTTP content negotiation or straightforward redirections where the PURL associated with the ontology points directly to the corresponding LODE documentation page.

Once published, the ontologies should be promoted and can be endorsed and adopted as standards.

Summary of Recommended Practices

In summary, the Recommended Practices for Ontology creation, publication, and maintenance for wind energy domain experts are:

- Ensure ontology alignment with existing semantic artefacts, consider re-use
- Balance expressiveness with simplicity
- Form working groups combining domain experts and knowledge engineers
- Use collaborative platforms
- Define a clear application use case before starting ontology work
- Follow established methods for ontology development
- Manage artefacts with version control
- Automate validation and publishing
- Engage the wider community with open calls and interactive reviews.
- Test early prototypes in real-world applications.
- Make ontologies FAIR
 - Publish ontologies on TechnoPortal or IndustryPortal
 - Assign versioned IRIs to all stable ontology releases
 - Delay PURL registration until ontology stabilisation
 - Provide machine- and human-readable documentation

References

De Nicola, A., Missikoff, M., and Navigli, R.: A Proposal for a Unified Process for Ontology Building: UPON, in: Database and Expert Systems Applications, edited by: Andersen, K. V., Debenham, J., and Wagner, R., Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 655–664, ISBN 978-3-540-31729-6, 2005.

Drobnjakovic, M., Kulvatunyou, B., Ameri, F., Will, C., Smith, B., and Jones, A.: The Industrial Ontologies Foundry (IOF) Core Ontology, in: Formal Ontologies Meet Industry (FOMI), CEUR Workshop Proceedings, Tarbes, France, ISSN 1613-0073, <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3240/paper3.pdf>, 2022

Emele, L., Stappel, M., Kleinau, A., Hastings, J., Sehn, V., Förster, H., Kuckertz, P., Hoyer-Klick, C., Hofmann, C., Knosala, K., Hülk, L., Killicarslan, I., Drathschmidt, F., Simon, F., Ulrich, F., Muschner, C., Winger, C., Neuhaus, F., Christmann, L., Glauer, M., Duc, P., Cordes, S., Pehl, M., Schnepf, K., Mossakowski, T., Stage, A., Gardian, H., Arellano Ruiz, E. S., Rothkötter, M., Rüllicke, L., Seibicke, A., Mittermeier, L., Müller, U., Köhler, N., Spinde, H., Wichern, V., Zielke, N., Stucky, U., Breikreutz, M., Gerlach, L., & Heidfeld, C. (2024). Open Energy Ontology (OEO) (Version 2.7.0) [Computer software]. <https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/ontology>

EPRI, Common Information Model (CIM) Primer: Eighth Edition, 2024. [Technical report 3002024188]

Gruber, T. R.: A translation approach to portable ontology specifications, *Knowl. Acquis.*, 5, 199–220, <https://doi.org/10.1006/knac.1993.1008>, 1993.

Guarino, N.: Formal Ontology in Information Systems: Proceedings of the 1st International Conference, Trento, Italy, 6–8 June 1998, IOS Press, NLD, 1st edn., ISBN 9051993994, 1998

Hogan, A., Blomqvist, E., Cochez, M., D'amato, C., Melo, G. D., Gutierrez, C., Kirrane, S., Gayo, J. E. L., Navigli, R., Neumaier, S., Ngomo, A.-C. N., Polleres, A., Rashid, S. M., Rula, A., Schmelzeisen, L., Sequeda, J., Staab, S., and Zimmermann, A.: Knowledge Graphs, *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 54, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3447772>, 2021

Marykovskiy, Y., Clark, T., Day, J., Wiens, M., Henderson, C., Quick, J., Abdallah, I., Sempreviva, A. M., Calbimonte, J.-P., Chatzi, E., and Barber, S.: Knowledge engineering for wind energy, *Wind Energ. Sci.*, 9, 883–917, <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-9-883-2024>, 2024.

Noy, N. F. and McGuinness, D. L.: *Ontology Development 101: A Guide to Creating Your First Ontology*, Stanford, 2001

Partridge, C., Mitchell, A., Cook, A., Sullivan, J., and West, M.: A Survey of Top-Level Ontologies – to inform the ontological choices for a Foundation Data Model, CDBB, <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.58311>, 2020

Zhou, A., Yu, D., and Zhang, W.: A research on intelligent fault diagnosis of wind turbines based on ontology and FMECA, *Adv. Eng. Inform.*, 29, 115–125, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2014.10.001>, 2015